

SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING ASSESSMENT – A MORE HOLISTIC METHODOLOGY FOR SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF FOOD PACKAGING

Mara Strenger¹, Alina Siebler¹, Markus Schmid¹

¹Sustainable Packaging Institute SPI, Faculty of Life Sciences, Albstadt-Sigmaringen University, Sigmaringen, Germany

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17301376
strenger@hs-albsig.de

Abstract: *Current packaging sustainability assessment methods do not consider packaging functionality in terms of packaging-related food loss and waste (food wastage) in a standardised way. However, packaging functionality should be considered when conducting a more holistic sustainability assessment, as food constitutes higher proportion of total resource consumption and consequently exerts a greater impact on sustainability in comparison to its packaging. Consequently, a more holistic sustainability assessment method for food packaging along its life cycle is needed. The present paper assesses the packaging functionality in relation to its dimensions, as outlined in ISO 18602:2013. Consequently, it is necessary to give due consideration to the distinct barrier requirements of specific food products, whilst seeking to minimise impacts on sustainability arising from packaging that is either oversized or undersized. To operationalise this balance, the Fit-for-Purpose Indicator (FFPI) has been developed, representing methodological progress compared to previous approaches. The FFPI facilitates a systematic assessment of whether a packaging concept adequately fulfils food-specific requirements without excessive material usage. This, in turn, supports both sustainability and food product protection agendas. The objective of the present paper is to facilitate a more holistic sustainability assessment, encompassing considerations of packaging functionality and ecological, economic and social sustainability aspects. To this end, the paper identifies and aligns suitable ecological, economic, and social assessment frameworks and combines them with the new FFPI. This approach is intended to ensure consistency and comparability across dimensions, thereby emphasising the importance of interpretable results, ideally via aggregated indicators such as single scores.*

Keywords: sustainability assessment method, food packaging, packaging-related food wastage, fit-for-purpose indicator

1 INTRODUCTION

Packaging, particularly for food, fulfils a variety of functions *Wohner, 2021*, the most important being product protection (*Dörnyei et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2017; Verghese et al., 2012*). Adequate product protection impacts the amount of food wastage (*Gruber et al., 2016; Pauer et al., 2019; Wikström & Williams, 2010; Williams & Wikström, 2011*), for example by extending the shelf life (*Wohner et al., 2019*). Food wastage refers to any food lost by deterioration or disposal. Thus, the term “wastage” encompasses both food loss and food waste (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2013; Uhlig et al., 2025). The product protection and the shelf-life depend on packaging functionality such as barrier and mechanical properties (*Lindh et al., 2016; Sasaki et al., 2021*). Given that globally around one third of

all food produced is not consumed (*Gustavsson et al., 2011*) and that avoiding food wastage could potentially reduce climate impact by up to 8 % (*Food and Agriculture Organization, 2013; Ecoplus et al., 2020*), it is necessary to realign the sustainability assessment of food packaging, taking into account packaging functionality and its influence on food wastage. Moreover, most resources in the packaging concept are usually linked to the food itself rather than the packaging (*Wohner, 2021; Wikström & Williams, 2010; Silvenius et al., 2013*). Since the protective function of packaging has a proportional impact on the amount of food wastage (*Gruber et al., 2016; Pauer et al., 2019; Wikström & Williams, 2010; Williams & Wikström, 2011*), it should be given top priority in reducing resource waste and potential environmental impacts of the food packaging concept.

Several studies have addressed this issue and integrate (packaging-related) food wastage into packaging life cycle assessment (LCA) and/or provide approaches how to do it. For instance Grant et al. (2015) propose a theoretical system expansion to include packaging-related food wastage, but without details on implementation or quantification (*Grant et al., 2015*). Heller et al. (2019) model 13 food packaging concepts to illustrate how food wastage affects the potential environmental impact of packaging concepts (*Heller et al., 2019*), while Manfredi et al. (2015) assess the impact of an antimicrobial packaging coating for milk packaging, focusing on shelf-life extension and reduced food wastage (*Manfredi et al., 2015*). However, these studies rely on generic waste rates rather than packaging-specific data. Wikström and Williams (2010) introduce a formula to include food wastage in packaging LCA but leave practical aspects of quantification unaddressed (*Wikström & Williams, 2010*). In contrast, Wohner et al. (2020) provide a more concrete example by measuring residual emptiability of ketchup packaging and incorporating the resulting food wastage into the LCA and economic assessment of the packaging (*Wohner et al., 2020*). Similarly, Silvenius et al. (2011) consider the effect of packaging size on food wastage using consumer survey data (*Silvenius et al., 2011*), and Yokokawa et al. (2018) explore consumer-related food losses from a behavioural perspective (*Yokokawa et al., 2018*). Conte et al. (2015) estimate food wastage for sheep's milk products by modelling waste probability based on shelf-life changes due to different packaging concepts, though the model relies heavily on assumptions and limited empirical data (*Conte et al., 2015*). In conclusion, these approaches highlight the importance of incorporating packaging functionality, although they remain largely theoretical or specific to individual cases. They highlight the challenges of systematically supplementing with packaging functionality and, by extension, the holistic sustainability assessment of packaging. Since sustainability is not only a question of potential environmental impacts but also economic and social aspects, a holistic sustainability assessment of food packaging should consider all these dimensions as well as the packaging functionality.

The aim of this research is to address the challenges that have been encountered to date and to develop an indicator that considers the functionality of packaging. The intention is to provide a standardised method for a more holistic assessment of food packaging that considers ecological, economic and social factors, as well as packaging functionality.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the following section 2.1, the assessment of the packaging functionality is first presented as a broadly applicable and practice-orientated implementation and represents the core of this paper. Subsequently, in section 2.2., the assessment of the ecological, economic and social dimensions of sustainability is briefly presented.

2.1 Assessment of packaging functionality

Packaging functionality, such as the barrier properties against gases and water vapour, have a strong influence on food safety and quality and therefore on the shelf life of the food (*Lindh et al., 2016*). Different foods also pose different demands on the barrier properties of packaging (Figure 6). For

example, sensitive products such as meat require high barriers against oxygen and, in some cases, light barriers to prevent light-induced autoxidation. On the other hand, respiring foods such as fruit and vegetables require a certain degree of gas exchange.

In addition to product-specific requirements, the functionality of packaging is assessed in accordance with the optimised packaging concept, as defined in ISO 18602:2013 (ISO, 2013). The ISO 18602:2013 approach is intended to balance the environmental impacts of overdimensioning (excessive material use) against those of underdimensioning (potential food wastage). In the light of these considerations, the objective of this paper is to assess the packaging functionality based on the optimal dimensioning in terms of fulfilment of food-specific requirements. Even though Figure 7 concentrates on the environmental impacts, analogous relations can also be observed for the economic and social impacts.

Figure 6: Specific barrier requirements of food products to their packaging, expressed as oxygen transmission rate and water vapour transmission rate, relevant to ensure product quality and shelf life. Translated from (Detzel et al., 2018).

2.2 Sustainability assessment frameworks and methods

For the sustainability assessment, suitable standards and methods are selected to ensure that the ecological, economic and social dimensions can be assessed in a maximally consistent and comparable manner. In accordance with this aim, the approaches for e.g. data collection, system boundaries, functional unit and implementation across the three dimensions are aligned as closely as possible. Moreover, it is imperative for the practical applicability of the results that they are as straightforward to interpret and communicate across all dimensions as possible, for example using aggregated indicators such as single scores per sustainability dimension. Although the aggregation of results simplifies communication, it also poses challenges. For instance, to ensure transparency, the weighting factors utilised must be disclosed. Caution should be paid to ensure that discrepancies in individual impact categories are not obscured and that relevant trade-offs, for example between different environmental impact categories or sustainability dimensions, remain visible.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Assessment of packaging functionality – Fit-for-Purpose Indicator

The assessment of packaging functionality in terms of optimum fulfilment of the food-related requirements is based on the developed Fit-for-Purpose-Indicator (FFPI). The FFPI is calculated from

the ratio of the food-related requirements for the barrier against oxygen and water vapour of the packaging and the actual barrier of the packaging (equation 1):

$$FFPI = \frac{\text{Optimal transmission rate food}}{\text{Transmission rate packaging}} \quad (1)$$

The food-specific requirements can be derived from existing literature values (see Figure 6) or from primary data in the form of manufacturer specifications. Subsequently, these values are then compared with the measured or calculated permeation properties (indicated as transmission rates) of the packaging to be assessed. Optimally dimensioned packaging results in an FFPI value of 1. Under-dimensioned packaging results in an FFPI value of less than 1. Over-dimensioned packaging results in an FFPI value of greater than 1. As a case example, minced meat (pork and beef) packaged in a flow pack under modified atmosphere (MAP) with a PP/EVOH/PA structure was assessed. The oxygen transmission rate of the packaging was 3.57 cm³/m² day, which lies within the food-specific requirement range of 2–20 cm³/m²·day (see Figure 6). This results in an FFPI value of 1. In contrast, the water vapour transmission rate of 1.92 g/m²·day was below the requirement range of 10–30 g/m²·day (see Figure 6), leading to an FFPI value of 5.21. Thus, while the packaging can be considered optimally dimensioned regarding oxygen permeability, it is over-dimensioned with respect to water vapour permeability.

Figure 7: Approach to the general conceptualization of an optimised packaging concept based on ISO 18602:2013 supplemented with the developed Fit-for-Purpose Indicator (FFPI) for optimally dimensioned packaging concepts regarding their functionality in terms of barrier properties.

3.2 More holistic Sustainability assessment of food packaging

Table 6 provides an overview of how ecology, economy and social aspects as well as packaging functionality are evaluated in the sustainability assessment methodology.

Table 6: Overview of the consideration and evaluation of the ecological, economic and social sustainability aspects of food packaging as well as the packaging functionality.

Packaging functionality	Ecological sustainability	Economic sustainability	Social sustainability
Assessment of fulfilment of the required product protection measured by the Fit for Purpose Indicator (FFPI)	Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of packaging based on ISO 14040/44:2021 and EU Recommendation 2021/2279	Life Cycle Costing (LCC) of packaging with costs of all material and energy flows	Social Life Cycle Assessment (sLCA) of packaging based on ISO 14075:2024

3.3 Discussion

The proposed approach offers the opportunity to assess the sustainability of food packaging in a more holistic way by integrating environmental, economic, social and functional packaging aspects. Notwithstanding this integrative perspective, the approach still has potential for improvement.

The FFPI does not account for the magnitude of impact resulting from over- or under-dimensioning in relation to the resource-intensity of the packaged food product. In this context, from an ecological and economic standpoint, overdimensioning may be regarded as more acceptable for resource-intensive food products than for those with a lower resource footprint. This is because the overall resource balance is more heavily weighted toward the food itself (Wohner et al., 2021; Wikström & Williams, 2010; Silvenius et al., 2013). Conversely, from a social ethics perspective, it cannot be determined that food requiring fewer resources should not be granted the requisite protection. The prevention of all manner of food wastage is of paramount importance, irrespective of the resource intensity, which is why it should be accorded a high degree of priority. Despite this, the differing resource intensity of various foodstuffs results in varied break-even points for the effects of packaging-related food wastage and packaging itself. To illustrate this point, one may consider the relative sustainability impact of a marginal increase in packaging input within the broader context of food packaging, particularly in the context of resource-intensive food products. Nevertheless, this differentiation has not yet been incorporated into the current application of the FFPI. To adequately reflect the resource intensity of the packaged food in sustainability assessments, packaging-related food wastage must be systematically integrated into LCA, LCC, and sLCA.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents an integrative approach for a more holistic sustainability assessment of food packaging by combining ecological, economic, and social assessment with a functionality-based assessment via the developed Fit-for-Purpose Indicator (FFPI). The approach enables to include the contribution of packaging to the preservation of food quality and safety as a significant factor influencing the sustainability of packaging. A limitation of the present approach that remains to be addressed is the integration of the four individual results (FFPI, ecological, economic and social assessment) into a single overall result. Notwithstanding, the approach offers a structured basis for identifying under- or overdimensioned packaging solutions regarding product protection. However, the current FFPI does not yet reflect the resource intensity of the packaged food. In order to more accurately reflect this, future developments should incorporate a consistent integration of packaging-related food wastage into the sustainability assessment of packaging. This would facilitate for a more differentiated, product-specific assessment of packaging concepts. Existing studies have addressed this issue in a case-specific manner. Nonetheless, there is an absence of consistent and systematic quantification of packaging-related food wastage across product categories. The authors of this paper are currently developing a methodological approach to close this gap and enable a more holistic and differentiated sustainability assessment of food packaging concepts.

Acknowledgments: *This work was supported by the Deutsche Bundesstiftung Umwelt [AZ 37233_01]. The authors would also like to thank the project partners from the Institute for Acoustics and Building Physics of the University of Stuttgart and the German Agricultural Society, who made a significant contribution to the project from which this publication emerged.*

5 REFERENCES

- Conte, A., Cappelletti, G.M., Nicoletti, G.M., Russo, C. & Del Nobile, M.A., 2015. Environmental implications of food loss probability in packaging design. *Food Research International*, 78, pp.11–17.
- Detzel, A., Bodrogi, F., Kauertz, B., Bick, C., Welle, F., Schmid, M., Schmitz, K., Müller, K. & Käß, H., 2018. *Biobasierte Kunststoffe als Verpackung von Lebensmitteln*.
- Dörnyei, K.R., Uysal-Unalan, I., Krauter, V., Weinrich, R., Incarnato, L., Karlovits, I., Colelli, G., Chrysochou, P., Fenech, M.C., Pettersen, M.K., Arranz, E., Marcos, B., Frigerio, V., Apicella, A., Yildirim, S., Poças, F., Dekker, M., Johanna, L., Coma, V. & Corredig, M., 2023. Sustainable food packaging: An updated definition following a holistic approach. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 7.
- ecoplus, BOKU, denkstatt & OFI, 2020. *Food Packaging Sustainability: A guide for packaging manufacturers, food processors, retailers, political institutions & NGOs*.
- Food and Agriculture Organization, 2013. *Food wastage footprint: Impacts on natural resources - Summary report*.
- Grant, T., Barichello, V. & Fitzpatrick, L., 2015. Accounting the impacts of waste product in package design. *Procedia CIRP*, 29, pp.568–572.
- Gustavsson, J., Cederberg, C. & Sonesson, U., 2011. *Global food losses and food waste: Extent, causes and prevention; study conducted for the International Congress Save Food! at Interpack 2011, [16–17 May], Düsseldorf, Germany*. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Heller, M.C., Selke, S.E.M. & Keoleian, G.A., 2019. Mapping the influence of food waste in food packaging environmental performance assessments. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 23(2), pp.480–495.
- International Organization for Standardization, 2013. *Packaging and the environment — Optimization of the packaging system; ICS 55.020, 13.020.01 (18602)*. Best Beuth Standards Collection.
- Lindh, H., Williams, H., Olsson, A. & Wikström, F., 2016. Elucidating the indirect contributions of packaging to sustainable development: A terminology of packaging functions and features. *Packaging Technology and Science*, 29(4–5), pp.225–246.
- Manfredi, M., Fantin, V., Vignali, G. & Gavara, R., 2015. Environmental assessment of antimicrobial coatings for packaged fresh milk. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 95, pp.291–300.
- Pauer, E., Wohner, B., Heinrich, V. & Tacker, M., 2019. Assessing the environmental sustainability of food packaging: An extended life cycle assessment including packaging-related food losses and waste and circularity assessment. *Sustainability*, 11(3), 925.
- Sasaki, Y., Orikasa, T., Nakamura, N., Hayashi, K., Yasaka, Y., Makino, N., Shobatake, K., Koide, S. & Shiina, T., 2021. Life cycle assessment of peach transportation considering trade-off between food loss and environmental impact. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 26(4), pp.822–837.
- Singh, P., Langowski, H.-C. & Wani, A.A., 2017. *Food Packaging Materials: Testing & Qand*. CRC Press.
- Silvenius, F., Grönman, K., Katajajuuri, J.-M., Soukka, R., Koivupuro, H.-K. & Virtanen, Y., 2013. The role of household food waste in comparing environmental impacts of packaging alternatives. *Packaging Technology and Science*, 27(4), pp.277–292.

Silvenius, F., Katajajuuri, J.-M., Grönman, K., Soukka, R., Koivupuro, H.-K. & Virtanen, Y., 2011. Role of packaging in LCA of food products. In: M. Finkbeiner, ed. *Towards Life Cycle Sustainability Management*. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, pp.359–370.

Social Hotspot Database, 2025. For more information. Available at: <http://www.socialhotspot.org/for-more-information.html> [Accessed 20 March 2025].

Uhlig, E., Sadzik, A., Strenger, M., Schneider, A.-M. & Schmid, M., 2025. Food wastage along the global food supply chain and the impact of food packaging. *Journal of Consumer Protection and Food Safety*.

Vergheze, K., Lewis, H. & Fitzpatrick, L., 2012. *Packaging for sustainability*. London: Springer.

Wikström, F. & Williams, H., 2010. Potential environmental gains from reducing food losses through development of new packaging - a life-cycle model. *Packaging Technology and Science*, 23(7), pp.403–411.

Williams, H. & Wikström, F., 2011. Environmental impact of packaging and food losses in a life cycle perspective: A comparative analysis of five food items. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 19(1), pp.43–48.

Wohner, B., 2021. *Nachhaltigkeitsbewertung von Verpackungen: Eine Empfehlung der ECR Austria Arbeitsgruppe "Nachhaltigkeitsbewertung"*.

Wohner, B., Gabriel, V.H., Krenn, B., Krauter, V. & Tacker, M., 2020. Environmental and economic assessment of food-packaging systems with a focus on food waste. Case study on tomato ketchup. *Science of the Total Environment*, 738, 139846.

Wohner, B., Kladnik, V., 2021. *Nachhaltigkeitsbewertung von Verpackungen: Eine Empfehlung der ECR Austria Arbeitsgruppe "Nachhaltigkeitsbewertung" 2021*.

Wohner, B., Pauer, E., Heinrich, V. & Tacker, M., 2019. Packaging-related food losses and waste: An overview of drivers and issues. *Sustainability*, 11(1), 264.

Yokokawa, N., Kikuchi-Uehara, E., Sugiyama, H. & Hirao, M., 2018. Framework for analyzing the effects of packaging on food loss reduction by considering consumer behavior. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 174, pp.26–34.